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A nested model of the Nordic Seas

by

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Abstract

The southeastern part of the Nordic Seas is among the longest (*Helland-Hansen and Nansen, 1909*) and most frequently sampled regions of the World Ocean. It is also, together with the Barents Sea, a region of high biological production. Mounting evidence shows that the biological production is closely related to the actual state of the marine climate in the region, particularly to the flow of warm, saline and nutrient-rich Atlantic Water across the Greenland-Scotland Ridge (GSR) (*Beaugrand and Reid, 2003*). Furthermore, the inflow of Atlantic Water keeps the Barents Sea and the waters south of Svalbard, ice free throughout the year, and is consequently of key importance for the local climate in western Scandinavia and north-western Russia. The salt transported into the Nordic Seas plays a fundamental role in the formation of intermediate waters in the region, and it is a key component in the formation of abyss water that occasionally takes place in the Greenland Sea. The thermodynamic transformation of Atlantic Water that takes place north of the GSR is thus also linked to the Atlantic thermohaline circulation (*Dickson and Brown, 1994*). A nested version of the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM) has been set up on the Nordic Seas in order to give a quantitative description of the changes in the main currents there. The nested model is initialized with interpolated model data from a global version of MICOM, has a horizontal resolution of 20-25 km, and a vertical resolution of 26 layers. It is forced by NCEP-NCAR synoptic forcing fields through the integration period from 1948-2003, and incorporates realistic river runoffs. The model has been favourably evaluated against observational data in the Iceland-Faroe-Scotland section and seems to reproduce variability of currents, temperatures and salinities quite well (*Hátun et al., 2005a,b; Eldevik et al., 2005*).

1 Introduction

The main objective of this work is to study the general circulation in the Nordic Seas in terms of a state-of-art isopycnic coordinate Ocean General Circulation Model (OGCM).

The model used in this study is a version of the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM), developed at the Rosenstiel School of Marine and Atmospheric Sciences at the University of Miami (*Bleck et al.*, 1992). The vertical discretizations of currently available ocean models can mainly be divided into z -coordinates, σ -coordinates and isopycnic coordinates. In z -coordinate models the depths of the coordinate surfaces are always constant in the horizontal direction. The σ -coordinate models introduce a vertical coordinate system which is scaled with depth as

$$\sigma = \frac{z - \zeta}{H + \zeta} \quad (1)$$

where z is the depth, H is the total ocean depth and ζ is the sea level elevation. This leads to a model with all coordinate surfaces located between the sea surface and the bottom of the ocean, so that the vertical resolution increases in shallow areas. Finally, in isopycnic coordinate models the density is used as a vertical coordinate. The main reason for this kind of vertical discretization is that most of the transport in the ocean is believed to occur along isopycnal surfaces. The cross-isopycnal mixing is order of magnitudes lower than the along-isopycnal mixing, and can in most model experiments be neglected, except for long term climate simulations, (*Ledwell et al.*, 1993). All numerical ocean models use advection schemes that contain numerical diffusion or mixing. In an isopycnic model, this artificial mixing will be directed along density surfaces, while ocean models using any other formulation in the vertical will introduce artificial diapycnal mixing whenever there are sloping isopycnals in the ocean which intersect the model coordinate surfaces. The isopycnic models therefore provide a mean for studying these mixing processes without introducing false diapycnal mixing through the numerical scheme used, and thereby maintaining water masses with specific $T - S$ properties. Another problem in numerical modelling is to maintain a sharp gradient across the pycnocline. Level coordinate models require very high vertical resolution to resolve the moving pycnocline, while an isopycnic model will always have the resolution where there are changes in density. The use of density as the vertical coordinate leads to some new numerical problems not present in traditional model formulations. Obviously, layers may disappear if the layer thicknesses approach zero. The layers will intersect the bottom topography and also outcrop to the mixed layer. Thus, advanced positive definite numerical advection routines are required to maintain positive layer thicknesses at all times.

In light of these results and a general curiosity of how MICOM is able to simulate, and eventually improve earlier model results of the general circulation in the Nordic Seas, MICOM is in this study set up on the North Atlantic and Nordic Seas. An evaluation of the model results with respect to the seasonal to decadal temperature variations in the Faroe-Shetland inflow waters has been performed by *Hátun et al.* (2005a), while the influence of the Atlantic Subpolar Gyre on the thermohaline circulation was studied in *Hátun et al.* (2005b). Another application of the model is described in *Eldevik et al.* (2004), where the model has been used to study the

pathways and export of Greenland Sea Water in terms of an advective-diffusive model and the currents fields from this model.

2 An overview of MICOM

The model system applied in this study is fully coupled to a sea-ice module consisting of the *Hibler III* (1979) rheology in the implementation of *Harder* (1996), and the thermodynamics of *Drange and Simonsen* (1996). It is a combination of a single-layer model of the oceanic mixed layer, based on a simple closure of the turbulence kinetic energy equation (*Gaspar*, 1988) and a three-dimensional isopycnic coordinate model of the stratified oceanic interior. The mixed layer has temporal and spatial varying density, while the interior layers have fixed potential densities. The specified potential densities of the sub-surface layers were chosen to ensure a realistic representation of the major water masses in the North Atlantic-Nordic Sea region (*Furevik et al.*, 2002). In the isopycnic layers below the mixed layer, temperature and layer thickness are the prognostic variables, whereas salinity is diagnostically determined by means of the simplified equation of state of (*Friedrich and Levitus*, 1972). The model presented here offers some advantages over conventional Cartesian coordinate models with regard to depicting subduction and thermohaline ventilation processes since the depth of the mixed layer is unambiguously defined at all times at every horizontal grid point. This allows us to draw a clear distinction between mixed layer and interior water.

2.1 The governing equations

The model solves the primitive equations consisting of the momentum equation for the velocity vector, the continuity equation for mass conservation, or in the isopycnic framework, for layer thickness, two conservation equations for heat and salt, and the hydrostatic equation relating pressure to depth (*Bleck and Boudra*, 1986), (*Bleck et al.*, 1989), (*Bleck and Smith*, 1990), (*Bleck et al.*, 1992), (*Bleck and Sun*, 1998).

2.2 Horizontal and vertical grid

The global model has a resolution of about 40 km over most of the North Atlantic whereas the nested model has twice that resolution. Otherwise the grid configurations of the two set ups are identical. In the horizontal, the model is configured with a local orthogonal grid mesh with one pole over North America and one pole over central Europe (*Bentsen et al.*, 1999), which gives a horizontal resolution of 20-25 km in the Nordic Seas in this model setup. Velocity and mass field variables are staggered horizontally such that u and v grid points are positioned halfway between mass grid points in x and y directions, respectively, which is known as the Arakawa C grid. The velocity vector and the thermodynamic variables are treated as layer variables that are vertically constant within layers but change discontinuously across layer interfaces. In the vertical, both models have 26 layers, where the uppermost is the thermodynamically active mixed layer while layers 2–26 are layers of constant specific volume $\alpha = \rho^{-1}$, where ρ is potential density with respect to surface pressure. In non-dimensional units of $(1 - \alpha/\alpha_0) \times 10^3$, the assigned coordinate values for the isopycnic layers are in the range $\sigma = 24.12 - 28.1$, where $\alpha_0 = 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$. Note that water masses lighter than 24.12 will be assigned to the mixed layer.

2.3 Bathymetry

The bathymetry is interpolated from the ETOPO5 data base (Data Announcement 88-MGG-02, Digital relief of the Surface of the Earth, NOAA, National Geophysical Data Center, Boulder, Colorado, 1988). It is corrected and adjusted in areas of special interest and importance such as in the Gibraltar Strait and at the Greenland-Scotland Ridge (GSR) to ensure that the dense water masses are able to exit at the right depths.

2.4 Atmospheric forcing

In the nested model, daily NCEP/NCAR re-analysis (*Kistler et al.*, 2001) fresh water, heat and momentum fluxes are used to force the system by applying the scheme of (*Bentsen and Drange*, 2000). If the model sea surface state for momentum and heat is close to the assumed sea surface state of the NCEP/NCAR re-analysis data, the turbulent fluxes for these variables are estimated by the atmospheric model used in the re-analysis data. This model uses bulk expressions to estimate the turbulent fluxes with the coefficients determined by (*Miyakoda and Sirutis*, 1986). If, however, the sea surface state differs significantly between the ocean model and the re-analysis data, the fluxes are modified. In combination with the Total Runoff Integrating Pathways (TRIP) data base, the NCEP/NCAR fields are also used to incorporate river runoff.

2.5 Surface relaxation

Mixed layer temperature and salinity fields are linearly relaxed towards the monthly mean climatological values of *Levitus et al.* (1994); *Levitus and Boyer* (1994), respectively. The e-folding relaxation time scale is set to 30 days for a 50 m thick mixed layer, and the relaxation is reduced linearly when the mixed layer depth exceeds 50 m. If the relaxation to the climatology were too strong, the model would not be able to reproduce the observed amplitude and phase shifts during the modelling period, due to the fixed seasonal properties of the climatology. The applied relaxation is rather weak, allowing for seasonal to inter-annual variations in the simulated mixed layer properties as shown in (*Hátun et al.*, 2005a).

2.6 Initial conditions

The model is initialized and nested with interpolated model data from a global version of MICOM (*Furevik et al.*, 2002), (*Bentsen et al.*, 1999). The data from the global model is simply interpolated to the nested grid with twice the resolution of the global model (Figure 1).

2.7 Model parameters

The diffusive velocities (diffusivities divided by the size of the grid cell) for layer diffusion, momentum dissipation, and tracer dispersion are 0.015 m s^{-1} , 0.015 m s^{-1} and 0.005 m s^{-1} , respectively. The diapycnal mixing coefficient K_d ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) is parameterized according to the *Gargett* (1984) expression $K_d = 3 \times 10^{-7}/N$, where N (s^{-1}) is the Brunt-Väisälä frequency. The

numerical implementation of the diapycnal mixing follows the scheme of *McDougall and Dewar* (1998).

2.8 Nesting conditions

The nesting approach applies a boundary relaxation scheme towards the outer (i.e. global) solution. This results in a so-called one way nesting where the boundary conditions of the regional model are relaxed towards the output from the global model. For the slowly varying baroclinic velocity, temperature, salinity and layer interface variables, this is a fully appropriate way to include the boundary conditions. For the barotropic variables, the relaxation approach requires careful tuning to avoid reflection of waves at the open boundaries. It is possible to compute the barotropic conditions exactly while taking into consideration both the waves propagating into and out of the regional model (see <ftp://micom.rsmas.miami.edu/bleck/openbdy.tex> for details). The regional model reads the global fields once a week and interpolates in time to specify the relaxation boundary conditions at each time step.

3 Model-model and observation-model comparisons

In this report, we have focused on output from three models. These are a 40 km resolution global version of MICOM and a 20 km resolution regional model, where the latter is a nested version of the former. The third model is the quarter-degree Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) North Atlantic/Arctic Ocean-Sea-Ice Model (NAOSIM) which uses levels of fixed depth as vertical coordinate. To illustrate similarities and differences between the models, the model results have been compared, and to find the degree of realism in the model results, they have been compared to observations. The fields to be discussed are the annual mean circulation at 150-m depth, the long-term mean and temporal variability of the volume transports, and the winter SST and SSS fields. *Drange et al.* (2005) perform a similar, but more extensive analysis with the global version of MICOM and the NAOSIM models to give an overview of the status of the prognostic modelling of the Nordic Seas marine climate system.

3.1 Simulated circulation in the Nordic Seas region

Figure 2 shows the observed surface circulation from the 1990s based on analyses of drifters (*Jacobsen et al.*, 2003) and the mean simulated circulation at 150-m depth from the three simulations for the period 1948-2002. In accordance with the observations, all simulations show the major inflow of Atlantic Water to the Nordic Seas east of Iceland and along the Scotland slope. In addition, there is a minor component west of Iceland. The inflow continues as the Norwegian Atlantic Current and the Norwegian Atlantic Slope Current through the Nordic Seas. At 70°N the flow splits into two branches, where one continues into the Barents Sea and the other towards the Fram Strait. In general, all systems show about the same circulation pattern, but the regional MICOM and NAOSIM produce a more realistic West Spitsbergen Current (WSC) which extends further north, even though it is stopped in the regional MICOM and

forced back south in the Fram Strait due to the nesting conditions from the global MICOM there. This indicates that the two-current system in the Fram Strait is dependent on the resolution of the model.

3.2 Simulated volume fluxes in the Nordic Seas region

Due to sparse current meter observations before 1994, the following discussion are split into to parts; the integration period 1950 to 2002, and the period 1994 to 2002. The simulated transports of heat and salt are strongly influenced by, or more or less proportional to, the volume fluxes (*Mauritzen et al.*, 2006). They are therefore not discussed here.

The total amount of water flowing northward across GSR is 9.8 Sv in the regional model, 9.2 Sv in the global model, and 9.3 Sv in NAOSIM. The northwards transport further into the Arctic is 6.7 Sv, 7.9 Sv, and 5.9 Sv, respectively. The corresponding numbers for the southward flow are 8.3 Sv, 8.6 Sv, and 9.5 Sv across GSR, and 5.5 Sv, 7.3 Sv, and 5.8 Sv across the Arctic sections. The net flow through the English Channel is small and about 0.1 Sv in the northward direction in all three models. An overview of possible explanations for different transport estimates in different model systems are given in *Drange et al.* (2005).

3.3 Comparison between simulated and observed volume fluxes in the Nordic Seas region

Table 2 in *Drange et al.* (2005) gives observed properties of the Atlantic Inflow for slightly different periods in the three openings at GSR. Estimates for the observed volume fluxes of Atlantic Inflow are 0.75 Sv in the Denmark Strait, 3.5 Sv in the Iceland-Faroe section, and 3.2 Sv in the Faroe-Scotland section. Corresponding values from the regional model in the period from 1994-2002 are 0.9 Sv, 4.7 Sv and 4.2 Sv, 0.8 Sv, 4.3 Sv, and 3.7 Sv from the global model, and 1.9 Sv, 3.4 Sv, and 4.0 Sv from the NAOSIM model. These results show that the regional model values are close to, but slightly higher than the global model values, and even higher than the observed values, except in the Denmark Strait. Experiments with the regional model show that the size of fluxes in the interior domain is sensitive to the implementation of the nesting conditions at the boundaries

3.4 Model-model comparison of the long-term temporal variability of the volume transports

Irrespective of the match between the actual size of the different simulated volume transports, and the observed values, one should expect that the models are able to reproduce the temporal variability of the transport anomalies, as they are driven by the same realistic atmospheric forcing fields. The anomalies of the simulated annual mean volume transports for the different models are shown in Figure 3. Correlations between transports in the same models are performed for each section around the Nordic Seas to see the effects of the different model types and resolution (Table 1). The best correlations are usually found, not surprisingly, between the regional and global MICOM. The largest differences are found in the Fram Strait where the

correlation between NAOSIM and the global MICOM is only 0.3708. Even though the regional MICOM is nested from the global MICOM with a nesting zone exactly in the Fram Strait, the regional MICOM is better correlated to NAOSIM than the global MICOM. This indicates that the model resolution is important to the flow in this area. The regional model is also closer to the NAOSIM results in the Denmark Strait and in the FSC.

3.5 Model results-observations comparison of the long-term temporal variability of the volume transports

To assess to which extent the model volume transports are realistic, they are compared with continuous high-quality current meter observations. Figure 4 shows observed and simulated northward volume transport through the Faroe-Shetland Channel. The regional model shows about the same variability as the observations, except for the summer months in 2001. Note that there are no observations from September 2001. The simulated volume fluxes from the regional model seems to be somewhat overestimated, while the those from the global model seems to be somewhat underestimated.

3.6 Simulated thermodynamic properties

Observed and simulated vertical temperature distributions along 75°N in the central Greenland Sea from July 1999 are shown in Figure 5. According to the observations, the warm poleward flowing Atlantic Water is located towards the east, where temperatures exceeding 6°C are found east of 5°E and to a depth of about 40 m. Temperatures below 0 are found below 50 m in the central Greenland Basin, while at the Greenland shelf, cold Polar Water flows south along with the return Atlantic Water at the Greenland continental slope. In the global model, the Atlantic Waters reach to 10°E and to a depth of about 40 m, while the corresponding numbers for the regional model are 6°E and 40 m.

3.7 Model-model comparisons of thermodynamic properties

The NAOSIM model seems to be less diffusive with respect to salinity than the MICOM models, with a narrow path of saline Atlantic water along the Norwegian coast (Figure 6). The temperature fields are more similar, probably caused by the strong influence of the common atmospheric forcing on the temperature in the models.

4 Conclusion

Numerical modelling of the Nordic Seas has been considerably improved the last years, despite the difficulties and challenges connected to the small inherent scale of oceanic motion, the large contrast between inflowing Atlantic and Arctic water masses, and the large fluctuations in fresh water fluxes (*Drange et al.*, 2005). Especially the mean exchanges in and out of the Nordic Seas have shown to agree well with observations, and also the interannual variations, although the simulated amplitudes tend to be less than the observed ones. The model comparison performed

Figure 1: The boundaries of the regional model where the regional model gets nesting conditions from the global model.

in this study shows that the regional MICOM and the NAOSIM have close values with respect to the mean flow in and out of the Nordic Seas, while the two MICOM models are closest with regard to variability. This might indicate that the model resolution, which is more or less the same in the regional MICOM and NAOSIM, is important to get mean flow through straits right, while the model design with respect to vertical discretization of layers, and also implementation of fluxes between atmosphere and ocean, are more decisive for the variability of volume fluxes between different basins. As demonstrated by the differences in both mean flow and variability, difficulties remain to be overcome, and further studies to clarify the causes is necessary.

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Section	Model-model	Correlation
BSO	Global MICOM-NAOSIM	0.7710
	Global MICOM-regional MICOM	0.7474
	NAOSIM-regional MICOM	0.7143
DEN	Global MICOM-NAOSIM	0.5577
	Global MICOM-regional MICOM	0.7563
	NAOSIM-regional MICOM	0.6873
FRA	Global MICOM-NAOSIM	0.3708
	Global MICOM-regional MICOM	0.7582
	NAOSIM-regional MICOM	0.4341
FSC	Global MICOM-NAOSIM	0.5870
	Global MICOM-regional MICOM	0.7390
	NAOSIM-regional MICOM	0.7331
IFR	Global MICOM-NAOSIM	0.6072
	Global MICOM-regional MICOM	0.6148
	NAOSIM-regional MICOM	0.5628

Table 1: Correlations between net transports in the three models for the Barents Sea Opening (BSO), the Denmark Strait (DEN), the Fram Strait (FRA), the Faroe-Shetland Channel (FSC) and the Iceland-Faroe Ridge (IFR).

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Figure 2: Observation-based near-surface circulation derived from drifters during the 1990s (upper left). Simulated velocity at 150 m by regional MICOM, averaged over the period 1950-2002 (upper right), global MICOM 1948-2002 (lower left) and NAOSIM 1948-2002 (lower right).

Figure 3: Simulated annual mean volume transport anomalies (Sv) for regional MICOM (thick), global MICOM (medium) and NAOSIM (thin lines). Left (right) column shows anomalies in net northward (southward) transports. The panels represent the Denmark Strait (upper), the Iceland-Faroe Ridge, the Faroe-Scotland section, the Barents Opening, and the Fram Strait.

Figure 4: Observed and simulated northward volume transport through the Faroe-Scotland Channel. Upper panel: Observed transport (Sv) based on current-meter measurements (*Østerhus et al.*, 2005) in dashed line, simulated regional (global) transport (Sv) in red (black) solid line. Middle panel: Corresponding volume flux anomalies, normalized with respect to the standard deviation of the respective time series. Lower panel: The number of days per month when observations were made.

Figure 5: Observed (upper left) and simulated temperature along 75°N in the Nordic Seas (regional MICOM to upper right, global MICOM to lower left and NAOSIM to lower right).

Figure 6: Simulated salinity (left) and temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) (right) in March, averaged over the uppermost 150 m of the water column for 1950-2002, as modelled by the regional MICOM (upper), global MICOM (mid) and NAOSIM (lower).